

Neutrosophic routes in multiverse of communication

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Abstract. Florentin Smarandache and Ștefan Vlăduțescu the authors and coordinators of the book “Communication Neutrosophic Routes”, published by Education Publishing, Ohio, USA, on 2014, are two remarkable professors, with many researches in neutrosophical, communication, mathematic, literature domains, social sciences. Logic is a fundamental component of advanced computer classes. Reference is constantly being made to how the rules of logic are incorporated into the fundamental circuits of a computer. The logic used in these classes is

known as classical or Boolean logic. Neutrosophic logic is an extension of classical logic, there are two intermediate steps between them. Neutrosophic logic is an idea generated by Florentin Smarandache. Like classical logic, it can be used in many ways, everywhere from statistics to quantum mechanics. Neutrosophy is more than just a form of logic however. Neutrosophic emergences are the unexpected occurrences of some major neutrosophic effects from the interaction of some minor qualitative elements.

Keywords: neutrosophy, multiverse of communication, neutrosophic communication routes

1 New ways of communication

Will really do the Humanity arrived to insensibility limit where it is just reason, where the feeling definitively lost its existential value? If it is true means that Albert Camus was right: only logical solution is suicide. To run from the darkness of the death, of the nightmares that ourselves generate them on its behalf, we have some solutions among which obvious suicide, or why not the optimism of the life spectacle. Suicide is <anti-A>; authentic beside the optimism represented by the neutrosophic <A>. If we accept the suicide or the equivalent or the <anti-A> is such as we should accept to spite ours face. As Brâncuși said that he is not creating the beauty, he only removes the idle material to be easier for us to identify the beauty beside him. As well in this study is defined (is removed) <anti-A> for the it's beauty and meaning, to be visible the beauty of our existence in front of its non-existence. Of the non-existence fears any existence, even the Universe itself, maybe only nonexistence itself is not afraid of itself, or maybe people who forget in their existence or do not know that they exist there. Likewise, we define (we remove) <anti-A> for the beauty and its meaning... to be visible the beauty of our existence in front of nonexistence (Smarandache F.).

The study “Communication Neutrosophic Routes” focuses on revealing the predominantly neutrosophic character of any communication and aesthetic interpretation. Neutrosophy, a theory grounded by Florentin Smarandache, is a coherent thinking of neutralities; differ-

ent from G.W. F. Hegel, neutrality is the rule, the contradiction is the exception; the universe is not a place of contradictions, but one of neutralities; the material and significant-symbolic universe consists predominantly of neutrality relationships. Any communication is accompanied by interpretation; sharply, aesthetic communication, by its strong ambiguous character, forces of the interpretation. Since, due to comprehension, description and explanation, the interpretation manages contradictions, understanding conflicts and roughness of reading, aesthetic interpretation is revealed as a deeply neutrosophic interpretation.

Communication and aesthetic interpretation prevalently manage neutralities but contradictions. As authors asserts, any manifestation of life is a component of communication, it is crossed by a communication passage. People irrepressibly generate meanings. As structuring domain of meanings, communication is a place where meanings burst out volcanically. Manifestations of life are surrounded by a halo of communicational meanings. Human material and ideatic existence includes a great potential of communication in continuous extension. The human being crosses the path of or is at the intersection of different communicational thoroughfares. The life of human beings is a place of communication. Consequently, any cognitive or cogitative manifestation presents a route of communication. People consume their lives relating by communicationaly. Some communicational relationships are contradictory, others are neutral, since within the manifestations of life there are found conflicting meanings and/or neutral meanings.

Communicational relations always comprise a set of neutral, neutrosophic meanings. Communication in general is a human manifestation of life with recognizable profile. Particularly, we talk about scientific communication, literary communication, pictorial communication, sculptural communication, esthetic communication and so on, as specific manifestations of life. All these include coherent, cohesive and structural series of existential meanings which are contradictory and/or neutral, neutrosophic. It can be asserted that in any communication there are routes of access and neutrosophic routes. Any communication is traversed by neutrosophic routes of communication.

2 Book content

The book is structured in ten chapters, each one presenting and arguing the novelty of neutrosophic concept in different areas. The studies in this book are application of the thesis of neutrosophic routes of communication and highlight neutrosophic paths, trajectories, itineraries, directions and routes in different forms and types of communication.

In Chapter 1, Florentin Smarandache and Ștefan Vlăduțescu develop the thesis of neutrosophic routes in the hermeneutics of text; they emphasize the fact that any text allows an infinity of interpretative routes: some based on linguistic-semiotic landmarks, others sustained by sociologic ideas, others founded by moral reference points, others founded by esthetic aspects and so on. A neutrosophic route can always be found in a text, that is a route of neutral elements, a thoroughfare of neutralities.

Professors Ioan Constantin Dima and Mariana Man reveal, in Chapter 2, that is not insignificant for a system to ensure that the events observed are representative for its universe, that they are observed in a precise, neutrosophic and coherent manner and that there are analysis patterns, deeds scientifically established to enable valid estimations and deductions.

In Chapter 3, Alexandra Iorgulescu (Associate Professor at the University of Craiova, Romania) decodes the neutrosophic inflections of Seneca's tragedies. Assistant Professor Alina Țenescu (University of Craiova) analyzes, in Chapter 4, in the non-space in contemporary French novel. The non-space is identified as a neutrosophic neutrality, which allows an application of the methodology and hermeneutics of neutrosophy. Finally, there is revealed a richness of meaning that provides the neutrosophic approach. In Chapter 5, Mădălina Strehie (Senior Lecturer at the University of Craiova, Romania) illustrates the communication as a key source of neutrality in Ancient Rome communication. In Chapter 6, the contribution of Daniela Gîfu (Senior Lecturer at the University of Iași, Romania) gives relevance to the "religious humor" in the reference system created by the two mega-concepts launched and imposed by Florentin Smarandache, neu-

troscopy and paradoxism. In Chapter 7, prepared by Professor Mihaela Gabriel Păun (a Romanian language and literature teacher), focuses on the neutrosophic determining of Romanian popular incidences in the brilliant sculptural work of Romanian artist Constantin Brâncuși (an unstoppable spiritual-aesthetic river appeared out of everyday folk tributaries). In Chapter 8, Professors Maria Nowicka-Skowron and Sorin Mihai Radu show that the major moments of reproduction are governed only by generally valid rules, and the main dimension of operating such an economy is the market and mechanisms of the market created in principle from the movement of prices according to the demand and supply ratio on the competitive market.

In Chapter 9, Professors Janusz Grabara and Ion Cosmescu demonstrate that being aware of the role that an information system in the company plays and its impact on individual processes, this article presents an information system used in the selected company. In Chapter 10, Bianca Teodorescu (from University of Craiova) shows that communication represents a category more enlarged than the information and has an ordinate concept; information is a part in the process of global communication.

Conclusion

The current book through its studies, represents a novelty in the field, a proof that neutrosophy is a domain of science that can be applied in any domain as interpretation of neutrality, a point of reference for students, master, doctoral, presenting ideas, principles, connections, relationships, interpretations of various fields as specificity, space and time.

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